

Testing the Equality of the Risk Difference in Multiple Comparative Trials

Soumik Banerjee* and Krishna Saha[†] [‡]

Abstract

In clinical trials, estimating risk difference (RD) is one of the most used epidemiologic indices to quantify the efficacy of a potential drug. In this paper, we develop some likelihood-based test procedures for testing the homogeneity of the risk difference based on the binomial model. Our goal is to develop a robust test procedure independent of the number of observations per center and the number of centers. The likelihood ratio test (LRT) based on the binomial likelihood shows significantly good results in terms of the type I error rate for medium and large number of observations per center irrespective of the number of centers. We also develop a score test or $C(\alpha)$ test based on binomial likelihood which requires the parameter estimates only under the null hypothesis. Our proposed test procedures are then compared with existing test procedures, by Monte Carlo simulations, in terms of size. Corrected variance non-parametric methods show better type I error rates for small number of observations per center irrespective of the number of centers. An illustrative application of the proposed test procedures is presented.

Key Words: Clinical Trials, Correlated Binary Data, Likelihood Ratio Test, Risk Difference, Test of Homogeneity.

1. Introduction

The common interest in the clinical trial is to investigate the efficacy of a new treatment versus a standard treatment. Due to difficulty recruiting subjects in clinical trial, a multicenter study design is used to collect the data. When the risk difference or treatment difference is constant across centers, we can average across centers to estimate a common risk difference between the new and the standard treatments. However, before doing this, it is desirable to determine whether the assumption of the homogeneity of the risk difference over centers holds.

Lipsitz et al. (1998) proposed various test procedures for testing the homogeneity of the risk difference in a multicenter randomized clinical trial when the data are sparse. However, in some situations, these test procedures showed serious liberal behaviors. To improve these test procedures, Lui and Kelly (2000) considered three different suggested approaches, but still these test procedures behave very similarly by showing improvement only in power. To overcome these limitations, We propose to improve the existing test procedures using the correct variance estimators by taking within center correlation into account.

We also develop model-based test procedures for testing the homogeneity of the risk difference. We propose likelihood ratio test (LRT) and $C(\alpha)$ test based on the binomial model. Our proposed test procedures are then compared with existing test procedures, by Monte Carlo simulations, in terms of size. An illustrative application of the proposed test procedures is presented.

*Department of Quantitative Sciences, Canisius University, Science Hall, Buffalo, NY 14208, USA

[†]Department of Mathematical Sciences, Central Connecticut State University, 1615 Stanley Street, New Britain, CT 06050, USA

[‡]Correspondence

1.1 Basic notations and definition

Suppose, we wish to compare two treatments using the data combined for K centers. For each of K centers, we randomly assign patients to one of the two treatment groups.

Let $\pi_{ij}, i = 1, 2, \dots, K; j = 1, 2$ be the corresponding cell probabilities of the outcome of interest. Then, $\hat{\pi}_{ij} = X_{ij}/n_{ij}$ is the sample estimate of this probability, where X_{ij} and n_{ij} are the number of successes and the number of subjects in the i th center and the j th treatment group, respectively. The risk difference τ_i in the i th center is simply $\pi_{i1} - \pi_{i2}$. We are interested in testing

$$H_0 : \tau_1 = \tau_2 = \dots = \tau_K = \tau, \quad (1)$$

where τ is a true common risk difference between the new and the standard treatments.

2. Hypothesis testing of checking the homogeneity of risk difference using non-parametric approach

The test procedures proposed by Lipsitz et al. (1998) and modified by Lui and Kelly (2000) are briefly discussed as follows:

Let $Y_i = \hat{\pi}_{i1} - \hat{\pi}_{i2}$, where the cell probabilities $\hat{\pi}_{ij} = X_{ij}/n_{ij}$ and X_{ij} 's are assumed to follow Binomial Distribution with $X_{ij} \sim \text{Bin}(n_{ij}, \pi_{ij}), i = 1, \dots, K$ and $j = 1, 2$. Then, the common risk difference τ is estimated as

$$\hat{\tau} = \frac{\sum Y_i / \hat{w}_i}{\sum 1 / \hat{w}_i}, \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{w}_i = \text{Var}(Y_i) = (\hat{\pi}_{i1}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i1}))/n_{i1} + (\hat{\pi}_{i2}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i2}))/n_{i2}$. When all n_{ij} are large, Fleiss (1981) suggested using the weighted least square test statistic as

$$Q_{WLS} = \sum (Y_i - \hat{\tau})^2 / \hat{w}_i. \quad (3)$$

When $\hat{w}_i = 0$ in Q_{WLS} , Lipsitz et al. (1998) suggested deleting the data in center i so that the sum is over $K' = K - q$ centers, where q is the number of centers in which $\hat{w}_i = 0$. Thus, as all $n_{ij} \rightarrow \infty, Q_{WLS} \sim \chi_{K'-1}^2$.

As an alternative to this chi-square approximation, when K is also large, Lipsitz et al. (1998) proposed the following test statistic

$$Z_{WLS}^2 = (Q_{WLS} - K')^2 / \sum [(Y_i - \hat{\tau})^2 / \hat{w}_i - 1]^2 \quad (4)$$

They claimed that the F-distribution with 1 and $K' - 1$ d.f. could provide a better approximation to the distribution of Z_{WLS}^2 than the chi-square distribution of Q_{WLS} with $K' - 1$ d.f.

From the simulation results, it can be seen that the above two proposed statistics Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 did not perform well when the mean treatment group per size center is not large. As a result, alternatively Lipsitz et al. (1998) proposed three other weighted test statistics as follows:

$$Z_{WLS,R}^2 = (Q_{WLS} - K')^2 / \sum [(Y_i - \hat{\tau})^2 / \hat{w}_i - 1]^2 \quad (5)$$

where the summation is over those centers in which the resulting $\hat{w}_i \neq 0$. When $K' (= K - q)$ and n_{ij} are large, Lipsitz et al. (1998) suggested that we employ the F distribution with 1 and $K' - 1$ d.f. to approximate the sampling distribution of $Z_{WLS,R}^2$. Lipsitz et al.

(1998) further argued that subtracting $K' - 1$ instead of K' from Q_{WLS} could provide an even better approximation of the sampling distribution of (5).

With the expectation of increasing the power of (5), Lipsitz et al. (1998) proposed the another test statistic as

$$Z_V^2 = \left[\sum ((Y_i - \hat{\tau})^2 - \hat{w}_i) / a_i \right]^2 / \sum [(Y_i - \hat{\tau})^2 - \hat{w}_i]^2 / a_i^2, \quad (6)$$

Where $a_i = \text{var}(Y_i - \tau)^2$. The approximate sampling distribution of Z_V^2 is an F distribution with 1 and $(K' - 1)$ d.f. as well.

Finally, to avoid the sensitivity of the above test statistic to small n_{ij} , when K is large, Lipsitz et al. (1998) proposed the following test statistic

$$Z_K^2 = \frac{[\sum ((Y_i - \hat{\tau}')^2 - \hat{w}_i) / ((1/n_{i1}) + (1/n_{i2}))^2]^2}{\sum [(Y_i - \hat{\tau}')^2 - \hat{w}_i]^2 / ((1/n_{i1}) + (1/n_{i2}))^4}, \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{\tau}' = \sum \frac{Y_i}{1/n_{1j} + 1/n_{2j}} / \sum \frac{1}{1/n_{1j} + 1/n_{2j}}$.

2.1 Example 1: CALGB Data

The data set in table 1 analyzed by Lipsitz et al. (1998) is from 21 institutions from the Cancer and Leukemia Group B (CALGB) randomized trial comparing two chemotherapy treatments with respect to survival (lived/died by the end of the study) in patients with multiple myeloma (Cooper et al., 1993). The 21 institutions accrued 156 patients, or 7.4 patients per institution. Note that, CALGB data-set is an example with high number of centers (K) and small average sample size (n).

The values of the above test statistics are $Q_{WLS} = 35.59$ (d.f.=15, p-value=0.002), $Z_{WLS}^2 = 14.12$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=15, p-value=0.001), $Z_{WLS,R}^2 = 1.50$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=15, p-value= 0.240), $Z_V^2 = 0.56$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=15, p-value=0.446) and $Z_K^2 = 0.48$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=20, p-value=0.498). From these results, we can see clearly that these above test statistics lead to very different conclusions. The test statistics Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 lead to rejecting the homogeneity, whereas other three test statistics $Z_{WLS,R}^2, Z_V^2$ and Z_K^2 lead to accepting the homogeneity. It can be seen from the simulation section that the test statistics Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 tend to have a Type I error rate that is higher than the nominal level when n_{ij} is small. In this given example, patients in each treatment per institution are very small.

2.2 Beta-binomial weight replacement

Lipsitz et al. (1998) considered that X_{ij}^t 's are assumed to follow the binomial model with $X_{ij} \sim \text{Bin}(n_{ij}, \pi_{ij})$, $i = 1, \dots, K$ and $j = 1, 2$. Based on this model, they calculated the weights w_i for their test approaches as the estimated variance of Y_i as

$$\hat{w}_i = \hat{\text{Var}}(Y_i) = (\hat{\pi}_{i1}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i1})) / (n_{i1} - 1) + (\hat{\pi}_{i2}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i2})) / (n_{i2} - 1).$$

The problem in the weights calculation is that they didn't consider the corrected model variance that can take into account the correlation between the observations within the centers for each treatment, that is, since patients from the same center are likely to have similar characteristics and to be tested by the same laboratory, patients within center most likely correlated.

Table 1: (CALGB Data) Patients with multiple myeloma (Cooper et al. 1993) .

Institute	n_{i1}	$\hat{\pi}_{i1}$	n_{i2}	$\hat{\pi}_{i2}$	$\hat{\pi}_{i1} - \hat{\pi}_{i2}$	\hat{w}_i
1	4	0.75	3	0.33	0.42	0.12
2	4	0.75	11	0.73	0.02	0.06
3	2	1.00	3	0.67	0.33	0.07
4	2	1.00	2	1.00	0.00	0.00
5	2	1.00	3	0.00	1.00	0.00
6	3	0.33	3	0.67	-0.34	0.15
7	2	1.00	3	0.67	0.33	0.07
8	5	0.20	4	1.00	-0.80	0.03
9	2	1.00	3	0.67	0.33	0.07
10	2	0.00	3	0.67	-0.67	0.07
11	3	1.00	3	1.00	0.00	0.00
12	2	1.00	2	0.00	1.00	0.00
13	4	0.25	5	0.20	0.05	0.08
14	3	0.67	4	0.50	0.17	0.14
15	4	0.50	6	0.67	-0.17	0.10
16	12	0.33	9	0.25	0.00	0.04
17	2	0.50	3	0.67	-0.17	0.20
18	3	1.00	4	0.25	0.75	0.05
19	4	0.25	3	0.67	-0.42	0.12
20	3	0.00	2	0.00	0.00	0.00
21	4	0.50	5	0.20	0.30	0.09

In this situation, we consider a correlated binomial model such as the beta-binomial model, that takes this within correlation into account, as $X_{ij} \sim BB(n_{ij}, \pi_{ij}, \phi_j)$, $i = 1, \dots, K$ and $j = 1, 2$. Then, the mean and variance of this model are, respectively, given by

$$E\{X_{ij}\} = n_{ij}\pi_{ij}$$

and

$$Var\{X_{ij}\} = n_{ij}\pi_{ij}(1 - \pi_{ij})\{1 + (n_{ij} - 1)\phi_j\},$$

where ϕ_j is the intra-class correlation coefficient for j th treatment. Using the above beta-binomial variance, we obtain the correct estimated weights \hat{w}_i^* as

$$\hat{w}_i^* = \frac{\hat{\pi}_{i1}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i1})(1 + (n_{i1} - 1)\hat{\phi}_1)}{n_{i1} - 1} + \frac{\hat{\pi}_{i2}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i2})(1 + (n_{i2} - 1)\hat{\phi}_2)}{n_{i2} - 1}.$$

These correct estimated weights can now be used to estimate the common risk difference τ as

$$\hat{\tau}^* = \frac{\sum Y_i / \hat{w}_i^*}{\sum 1 / \hat{w}_i^*}$$

to obtain the earlier two weighted test statistics Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 . Note that the intra-class correlation coefficients ϕ_j can be estimated along the lines of Fleiss (1981) and Ridout et al. (1999). The estimator $\hat{\phi}$, in terms of the data (y_i, n_i) , is obtained as

$$\hat{\phi}_{AOV} = (\sigma_b^2 - \sigma_w^2) / (\sigma_b^2 + (n^* - 1)\sigma_w^2),$$

where $\sigma_b^2 = [1/(m-1)][\sum Y_i^2/n_i - (1/N)(\sum Y_i)^2]$, $\sigma_w^2 = [1/(N-m)][\sum Y_i - \sum Y_i^2/n_i]$,

$N = \sum n_i$ and $n^* = [1/(m-1)][N - \sum n_i^2/N]$. First, using the above ANOVA approach we obtain the estimates of the intra-class correlation coefficients for treatment 1 and treatment 2, respectively, as $\hat{\phi}_1 = 0.2083$ and $\hat{\phi}_2 = 0.1159$. Based on these estimates of the intra-class correlation coefficients, we obtain the correct weights and then recalculated the test statistics describes above. The values of the test statistics are given as follows: $Q_{WLS} = 23.57$ (d.f.=15, p-value=0.069), $Z_{WLS}^2 = 2.56$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=15, p-value=0.129), $Z_{WLS,R}^2 = 3.7$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=15, p-value=0.073), $Z_V^2 = 0.57$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=15, p-value=0.446) and $Z_K^2 = 1.28$ (d.f.1=1, d.f.2=20, p-value=0.270). From these results, it can be seen that all the test statistics are leading to the same conclusion. What it tells that the test statistics based on the corrected weights has improved, particularly the performance of the test statistics Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 , which are commonly used to test the homogeneity of the risk differences.

2.3 Simulation Studies

Following Lui and Kelly (2000), we conducted the simulation study to check the performance of our propose corrected test statistics, particularly Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 . We follow exactly same parameter values used by Lui and Kelly (2000) to generate the random data. As mentioned, the probability π_{i2} varies between centers due to center effects, we set $\pi_{i2} = .10 + .70p$, where p is generated from a beta distribution with mean $\pi = \alpha/(\alpha + \beta)$ and variance $\pi(1 - \pi)/(T + 1)$ with $T = \alpha + \beta$. We then set $\pi_{i1} = \pi_{i2} + 0.1$, which indicates that the underlying common risk difference τ is 0.10 over all centers. Note that p follows the beta distribution with $T=2$ and $\pi = 0.5$ is equivalent to assuming that p follows a uniform distribution on $(0, 1)$. We generate the sample size n_{ij} following the probability mass function $f(n_{ij}) = 0.20$ for $n_{ij} = n - s$, where n is a given fixed constant and $s = 2, 1, 0, -1, -2$. Moreover, we consider the probability π for the underlying beta distribution equals 0.50; the intra-class correlation $\rho (= 1/[2(T+1)])$ ranges from approximately 0.05 to 0.4; the number of centers K equals 8, 16, 32, 48, 96; and the mean treatment group size per center $E(n_{ij}) = n$ equals 4, 8 and $(\alpha = 1, \beta = 1)$, $(\alpha = 5, \beta = 4)$. For each configuration, we generated 10,000 repeated samples and calculated the Type I error rates for the test statistics Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 obtained based on both version of the weights, assuming the binomial distribution as well as the beta-binomial distribution. These results are shown in Table 2 and Table 3 below.

Table 2: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(1, 1)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/6, n = 4$

K	$Q_{WLSPrev}$	Q_{WLSnew}	$Z_{WLSPrev}^2$	Z_{WLSNew}^2
8	0.203	0.126	0.545	0.096
16	0.320	0.115	0.271	0.086
32	0.488	0.092	0.435	0.081
48	0.605	0.071	0.551	0.063
96	0.834	0.099	0.791	0.065

Table 3: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(5, 4)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/20, n = 8$

K	$Q_{WLSPrev}$	Q_{WLSnew}	$Z_{WLSPrev}^2$	Z_{WLSNew}^2
8	0.130	0.051	0.093	0.036
16	0.17	0.055	0.135	0.041
32	0.247	0.058	0.211	0.057
48	0.297	0.051	0.253	0.063
96	0.431	0.049	0.373	0.063

From Tables 2 and 3, we can clearly see that both the test statistics based on the corrected weights perform much better for all situations considered here, particularly for $\rho = 1/20$ and $n = 8$, where both test statistics are maintaining the Type I error rate very close to the nominal. However, this approach fails to deliver the desired result when the average sample size is high.

3. Likelihood-Based Test Procedures

In this section, we develop some likelihood-based test procedures for testing the homogeneity of the risk difference based on the binomial model. We develop both LRT (Likelihood Ratio Test) and $c(\alpha)$ test as follows.

3.1 LRT Based on Binomial Model

Let X_{ij} , be the counts of the i th center and the j th treatment group. We will assume $X_{ij} \sim Bin(n_{ij}, \pi_{ij})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$; $j = 1, 2$ with the p.m.f as

$$f(X_{ij}|\pi_{ij}) = \binom{n_{ij}}{\pi_{ij}} \pi_{ij}^{x_{ij}} (1 - \pi_{ij})^{n_{ij} - x_{ij}}, i = 1, 2, \dots, K; j = 1, 2. \quad (8)$$

Then, the likelihood and the log-likelihood can be written as

$$L = \prod_i \prod_j \binom{n_{ij}}{\pi_{ij}} \pi_{ij}^{x_{ij}} (1 - \pi_{ij})^{n_{ij} - x_{ij}} \text{ and}$$

$$\ln L = \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} + \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \pi_{i1} + \sum_i x_{i2} \ln \pi_{i2} + \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln (1 - \pi_{i1})$$

$$+ \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln (1 - \pi_{i2}),$$

Recall that $\lambda_i = \pi_{i2} - \pi_{i1}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K \implies \pi_{i2} = \lambda_i + \pi_{i1}$. Based on this, we can rewrite the log-likelihood as

$$\ln L = \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} + \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \pi_{i1}$$

$$+ \sum_i x_{i2} \ln (\lambda_i + \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln (1 - \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln (1 - \lambda_i - \pi_{i1}).$$

Let $\ln L_0$ and $\ln L_a$ be the maximum log-likelihoods under the null H_0 and the alternative H_a hypotheses, respectively. Then, the LRT statistic for testing H_0 against H_a can be obtained as

$$\text{lrt} = 2[\ln L_a - \ln L_0] \sim \chi_{K-1}^2,$$

as $n_{ij} \rightarrow \infty$. Which reduces to

$$2\{ \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \hat{\pi}_{i1} + \sum_i x_{i2} \ln (\hat{\lambda}_i + \hat{\pi}_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln (1 - \hat{\pi}_{i1})$$

$$+ \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln (1 - \hat{\lambda}_i - \hat{\pi}_{i1}) \} - \{ \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \hat{\pi}_{i1H0} + \sum_i x_{i2} \ln (\hat{\lambda}_{H0} + \hat{\pi}_{i1H0})$$

$$+ \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln (1 - \hat{\pi}_{i1H0}) + \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln (1 - \hat{\lambda}_{H0} - \hat{\pi}_{i1H0}) \},$$

where $\hat{\pi}_{i1}$ and $\hat{\lambda}_i$ are the unrestricted MLEs of the parameters π_{i1} and λ_i , respectively, whereas $\hat{\pi}_{i10}$ and $\hat{\lambda}_0$ are the MLEs of the parameters π_{i1} and λ_0 , respectively, under H_0 . These MLEs can be easily obtained by maximizing the maximum log-likelihoods $\ln L_0$ and $\ln L_a$ discussed above. Alternatively, one can solve the maximum likelihood equations of those parameters to obtain those MLE estimates.

3.2 CALGB Data Analysis Based on Binomial LRT

For the CALGB dataset, the number of clusters $K = 21$ and the average cluster sizes for the treatment and control groups are $\bar{n}_1 = 3.4$ and $\bar{n}_2 = 4$, respectively. We implemented the likelihood ratio test assuming binomial model discussed above on the CALGB data. The ML estimates are obtained by maximizing the corresponding log-likelihoods using R. The values of the LR test statistic and the p-value are 4.89 and 0.99, respectively. The LRT method assuming binomial method leads to the same conclusion as shown by the previous methods.

3.3 Simulation Results for LRT

To validate the LR tests for binomial model, we have run simulation for different combinations of the number of clusters (K), average cluster sizes (n) and intra-class correlation coefficient (ρ) and obtain the type-I error rate as before. The results for binomial model are presented in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

Table 4: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(4, 5)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/20$

K	n=8	n=10	n=15	n=20	n=25	n=30	n=40	n=60
8	0.076	0.076	0.059	0.062	0.061	0.059	0.052	0.052
16	0.088	0.079	0.069	0.069	0.053	0.061	0.052	0.063
20	0.094	0.079	0.065	0.063	0.063	0.068	0.059	0.061
30	0.101	0.089	0.079	0.068	0.062	0.061	0.059	0.060

Table 5: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(2, 2)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/4$

K	n=8	n=10	n=15	n=20	n=25	n=30	n=40	n=60
8	0.055	0.065	0.052	0.066	0.061	0.046	0.056	0.061
16	0.061	0.069	0.064	0.064	0.066	0.061	0.049	0.058
20	0.071	0.070	0.068	0.069	0.049	0.058	0.051	0.061
30	0.078	0.073	0.068	0.069	0.062	0.061	0.058	0.060

Table 6: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(1, 1)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/2.2$

K	n=8	n=10	n=15	n=20	n=25	n=30	n=40	n=60
8	0.055	0.065	0.052	0.058	0.061	0.044	0.056	0.051
16	0.049	0.044	0.052	0.061	0.069	0.057	0.064	0.058
20	0.045	0.052	0.065	0.065	0.061	0.059	0.061	0.054
30	0.055	0.054	0.047	0.062	0.061	0.065	0.068	0.060

From Tables 4, 5 and 6, we can conclude that LRT for Binomial model is working fine for both low and high number of clusters, sample size and intra-class correlation coefficients.

4. $C(\alpha)$ test Based on Binomial Model

Assuming $X_{ij} \sim Bin(n_{ij}, \pi_{ij}), i = 1, 2, \dots, K; j = 1, 2$, and from section (3.1), we observe that the log-likelihood can be written as

$$l = \ln L = \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} + \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \pi_{i1} \\ + \sum_i x_{i2} \ln(\lambda_i + \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln(1 - \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln(1 - \lambda_i - \pi_{i1}).$$

Now, we develop procedures for testing the composite hypothesis $H_0 : \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \dots = \lambda_K = \lambda$ against H_a : at least two λ_i 's are not the same. For the convenience of the derivation of the $C(\alpha)$ statistics, we reparameterize λ_i under H_a by $\lambda_i = \lambda + \alpha_i, i = 1, \dots, K - 1$, with $\alpha_K = 0$. Then testing $H_0 : \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \dots = \lambda_K = \lambda$ reduces to testing $H_0 : \alpha_1 = \dots = \alpha_{K-1} = 0$. Let $\alpha' = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{K-1})$ and $\omega' = (\lambda, \pi_{i1}, \pi_{i2}, \dots, \pi_{ik})$, with ω' being treated as nuisance parameter. Let's denote

$$U = \frac{\delta l}{\delta \alpha} | \alpha = 0$$

$$V = \frac{\delta l}{\delta \omega} | \alpha = 0$$

$$A = E\left(-\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha \delta \alpha'} | \alpha = 0\right)$$

$$C = E\left(-\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha \delta \omega} | \alpha = 0\right)$$

$$D = E\left(-\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \omega \delta \omega'} | \alpha = 0\right)$$

The dimensions of the matrices U; V; A; C and D are, respectively, $(K - 1) \times 1, (K + 1) \times 1, (K - 1) \times (K - 1), (K - 1) \times (K + 1)$, and $(K + 1) \times (K + 1)$, The $C(\alpha)$ test (Neyman, 1959; Saha, 2013) based on the residual,

$$S(\omega) = U(\omega) - \beta' V(\omega) I \quad (9)$$

with the partial regression coefficients $\beta' = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{K+1})$ and $I = (1, \dots, 1)'$ being the column vector of $(K - 1)$ order, for testing H_0 against H_a is given by

$$\hat{S}(\hat{A} - \hat{C} \hat{D}^{-1} \hat{C}')^{-1} \hat{S}', \quad (10)$$

which asymptotically follows χ_{K-1}^2 as $n_{ij} \rightarrow \infty$. Now, after replacing the nuisance parameter ω by it's consistent/ML estimate under H_0' , it can be shown that the term $\hat{\beta}' V(\hat{\omega}) I = 0$. (KK Saha 2013). After re parameterization, the modified log likelihood becomes,

$$l = \ln L = \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} + \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \pi_{i1} \\ + \sum_i x_{i2} \ln(\lambda + \alpha_i + \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln(1 - \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln(1 - \lambda - \alpha_i - \pi_{i1}).$$

Now, the structures of the matrices will be as follows.

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta l}{\delta \alpha_1} | \alpha_1 = 0 \\ \frac{\delta l}{\delta \alpha_2} | \alpha_2 = 0 \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\delta l}{\delta \alpha_{(K-1)}} | \alpha_{(K-1)} = 0 \end{pmatrix}, V = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta l}{\delta \lambda} | \alpha_i = 0 \\ \frac{\delta l}{\delta \pi_{i1}} | \alpha_1 = 0 \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\delta l}{\delta \pi_{K1}} | \alpha_K = 0 \end{pmatrix}, A = E - \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_1^2} | \alpha_1 = 0 & & & \\ & \ddots & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_{(K-1)}^2} | \alpha_{(K-1)} = 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$C = E - \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_1 \delta \lambda} | \alpha_1 = 0 & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_1 \delta \pi_{11}} | \alpha_1 = 0 & \dots & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_1 \delta \pi_{K1}} | \alpha_1 = 0 \\ -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_2 \delta \lambda} | \alpha_2 = 0 & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_2 \delta \pi_{11}} | \alpha_2 = 0 & \dots & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_2 \delta \pi_{K1}} | \alpha_2 = 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_{(K-1)} \delta \lambda} | \alpha_{(K-1)} = 0 & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_{(K-1)} \delta \pi_{11}} | \alpha_{(K-1)} = 0 & \dots & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha_{(K-1)} \delta \pi_{K1}} | \alpha_{(K-1)} = 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$D = E - \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \lambda^2} | \alpha = 0 & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \lambda \delta \pi_{11}} | \alpha = 0 & \dots & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \lambda \delta \pi_{K1}} | \alpha = 0 \\ -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \pi_{11} \delta \lambda} | \alpha = 0 & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \pi_{11}^2} | \alpha = 0 & \dots & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \pi_{11} \delta \pi_{K1}} | \alpha = 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \pi_{K1} \delta \lambda} | \alpha = 0 & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \pi_{K1} \delta \pi_{11}} | \alpha = 0 & \dots & -\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \pi_{K1}^2} | \alpha = 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

After some basic algebra, we can observe that the matrices U, V, A, C and D can be expressed as

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{x_{12}}{\lambda + \pi_{11}} - \frac{n_{12} - x_{12}}{1 - \lambda - \pi_{11}} \\ \frac{x_{22}}{\lambda + \pi_{21}} - \frac{n_{22} - x_{22}}{1 - \lambda - \pi_{21}} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{x_{(K-1)2}}{\lambda + \pi_{(K-1)1}} - \frac{n_{(K-1)2} - x_{(K-1)2}}{1 - \lambda - \pi_{(K-1)1}} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{n_{12}\pi_{12}}{(\lambda + \pi_{11})^2} + \frac{n_{12} - n_{12}\pi_{12}}{(1 - \lambda - \pi_{11})^2} & & & \\ & \ddots & & \\ & & \frac{n_{(K-1)2}\pi_{(K-1)2}}{(\lambda + \pi_{(K-1)1})^2} + \frac{n_{(K-1)2} - n_{(K-1)2}\pi_{(K-1)2}}{(1 - \lambda - \pi_{(K-1)1})^2} & \end{pmatrix},$$

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{n_{12}}{\pi_{12}} + \frac{n_{12}}{(1 - \pi_{12})} & \frac{n_{12}}{\pi_{12}} + \frac{n_{12}}{(1 - \pi_{12})} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \frac{n_{22}}{\pi_{22}} + \frac{n_{22}}{(1 - \pi_{22})} & 0 & \frac{n_{22}}{\pi_{22}} + \frac{n_{22}}{(1 - \pi_{22})} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \frac{n_{32}}{\pi_{32}} + \frac{n_{32}}{(1 - \pi_{32})} & 0 & \dots & \frac{n_{32}}{\pi_{32}} + \frac{n_{32}}{(1 - \pi_{32})} & \dots & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{n_{(K-1)2}}{\pi_{(K-1)2}} + \frac{n_{(K-1)2}}{(1 - \pi_{(K-1)2})} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{n_{(K-1)2}}{\pi_{(K-1)2}} + \frac{n_{(K-1)2}}{(1 - \pi_{(K-1)2})} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} \sum \left(\frac{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{1-\pi_{i2}} \right) & \cdot & \frac{n_{K2}}{\pi_{K2}} + \frac{n_{K2}}{(1-\pi_{K2})} \\ \cdot & \cdot & 0 & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & 0 & \frac{n_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i1}}{(1-\pi_{i1})} + \frac{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{(1-\pi_{i2})} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \frac{n_{K2}}{\pi_{K2}} + \frac{n_{K2}}{(1-\pi_{K2})} & \cdot & \frac{n_{K1}}{\pi_{K1}} + \frac{n_{K1}}{(1-\pi_{K1})} + \frac{n_{K2}}{\pi_{K2}} + \frac{n_{K2}}{(1-\pi_{K2})} \end{pmatrix}$$

We estimate the matrices A; C and D after replacing the parameters λ , π_{i1} with their corresponding ML estimates under H_0 . The ML estimates of λ , π_{i1} and π_{i2} , ($\hat{\lambda}$, $\hat{\pi}_{i1}$, $\hat{\pi}_{i2}$) can be found solving the equations below:

$$\sum \left(\frac{x_{i2}}{\lambda + \pi_{i1}} - \frac{n_{i2} - x_{i2}}{1 - \lambda - \pi_{i1}} \right) = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{x_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} - \frac{n_{i1} - x_{i1}}{1 - \pi_{i1}} + \frac{x_{i2}}{\lambda + \pi_{i1}} - \frac{n_{i2} - x_{i2}}{1 - \lambda - \pi_{i1}} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\pi_{i2} = \lambda + \pi_{i1}. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, we can maximize the log likelihood function using R software to obtain the MLEs of the parameters.

4.1 CALGB Data Analysis Based on Binomial $C(\alpha)$ test

For the CALGB dataset, the number of clusters $K = 21$ and the average cluster sizes for the treatment and control groups are $\bar{n}_1 = 3.4$ and $\bar{n}_2 = 4$, respectively. We implemented the $C(\alpha)$ test assuming binomial model discussed above on the CALGB data. The ML estimates are obtained by maximizing the corresponding log-likelihoods using R. The values of the LR test statistic and the p.value are 14.304 and 0.814, respectively. The $C(\alpha)$ method assuming binomial method leads to the same conclusion as shown by the previous methods.

4.2 Simulation Results for $C(\alpha)$ test

To validate the $C(\alpha)$ tests for binomial model, we have run simulation for different combinations of the number of clusters (K), average cluster sizes (n) and intra-class correlation coefficient (ρ), and obtain the type-I error rate as before. The results for binomial model are presented in Tables 7, 8 and 9.

Table 7: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(4, 5)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/20$

K	n=8	n=10	n=15	n=20	n=25	n=30	n=40	n=60
8	0.088	0.063	0.055	0.046	0.051	0.049	0.042	0.052
16	0.082	0.071	0.069	0.061	0.063	0.042	0.058	0.056
20	0.088	0.079	0.056	0.063	0.064	0.051	0.045	0.057
30	0.112	0.089	0.061	0.068	0.056	0.064	0.046	0.063

Table 8: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(2, 2)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/10$

K	$n=8$	$n=10$	$n=15$	$n=20$	$n=25$	$n=30$	$n=40$	$n=60$
8	0.083	0.069	0.055	0.065	0.056	0.058	0.053	0.049
16	0.087	0.081	0.067	0.061	0.060	0.049	0.055	0.056
20	0.099	0.086	0.064	0.041	0.059	0.051	0.061	0.054
30	0.101	0.095	0.061	0.065	0.062	0.057	0.063	0.055

Table 9: Type I error rate for the simulation from a $Beta(1, 1)$ distribution 5000 replications: $\rho = 1/6$

K	$n=8$	$n=10$	$n=15$	$n=20$	$n=25$	$n=30$	$n=40$	$n=60$
8	0.112	0.093	0.084	0.066	0.058	0.062	0.054	0.050
16	0.123	0.099	0.089	0.069	0.062	0.046	0.056	0.051
20	0.141	0.112	0.085	0.079	0.066	0.064	0.054	0.055
30	0.183	0.151	0.085	0.083	0.064	0.061	0.059	0.061

From Tables 7, 8 and 9, we can conclude that the $C(\alpha)$ test for binomial model is working fine for both low and high number of clusters, along with a high sample size and intra-class correlation coefficients.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed three different approaches for testing the homogeneity of risk differences in a multi-center clinical trial. Our goal is to develop a robust test procedure which doesn't depend on the number of clusters, sample size and intra-class correlation coefficient.

Initially, we replaced the binomial weights with beta-binomial weights and observed a significant improvement in the type-I error rate for small average sample size. However, this method didn't work for high sample size.

Next, we developed likelihood ratio test assuming binomial distribution. The ML estimates of the parameters under H_0 and H_a have been obtained using the "nlm" function in R software. This test procedure is working fine for both low and high number of clusters, sample size and intra-class correlation coefficient.

Finally, we have developed $C(\alpha)$ test assuming binomial distribution which requires parameter estimation only under H_0 . This procedure is working fine for both low and high number of clusters, intra-class correlation coefficient and a relatively high sample size.

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